

Integrating libraries and Digital Humanities

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The digital turn in the dissemination of knowledge has shaken libraries to their core in many ways. One of these ways is the field of Digital Humanities, and especially the cooperation between libraries and its research community. This role of libraries within DH has been discussed extensively in an international (mostly US) context, but not at DH Benelux (see <http://libereurope.eu/blog/2018/02/05/digital-humanities-reading-list-part-2/> for a selection). In this Round Table we would like to address the question: does every digital humanist need a library? What do digital humanists need from libraries, beyond digitizing special collections and cultural heritage? What do libraries do to facilitate researchers in finding, using (and that includes mining), producing, reviewing and publishing (open) academic content? Do these expectations and activities match or are there blind spots? An international panel consisting of both researchers and librarians takes the lead in debating this.

The panel consists of Hilde de Weerd (professor of Chinese History and head of the Leiden University Centre for Digital Humanities, Leiden University), Ulrike Wuttke (Postdoctoral Research Fellow for Project PARTHENOS, University of Applied Sciences Potsdam), Sally Chambers (Digital Humanities Research Coordinator, Ghent University) and Max Kemman (PhD-student, University of Luxembourg).

One of the frames we would like to use to explore this question is that of Open Science, with its fundamentally new possibilities also enabled by the digital turn. UKB (the Dutch consortium of the thirteen university libraries and the National Library of the Netherlands) has been an active partner in the Dutch National Platform Open Science. Within this platform CLARIAH is also recognized as an important node in the research infrastructure available for Humanities (<https://www.openscience.nl/en/open-science-in-the-netherlands/current-activities/index>). Connections between Open Science and digital humanities are also explored in the context of DARIAH (e.g. <https://dariah2018.sciencesconf.org/>). The open culture of digital humanities strongly resonates with the principles of Open Science. At DH2017 in Montréal, one of the keynotes was by Marin Dacos, who is the director of the Center for open electronic publishing and scientific advisor for open science to the director-general of research and innovation at the Ministry for Research in France. With these strong mutual ties with Open Science, could this be one of the new ways for collaboration between researchers and libraries?

This Round Table is organized by the UKB working group on DH (<https://www.ukb.nl/werkgroep-digital-humanities>). It started in 2017 to improve the activities of the partner libraries for DH through knowledge exchange and collaboration.